
ABSTRACT

**An Investigation of Statistical Measures for Intensity Comparison
of Process Patterns in Analog Wafer Test Data**

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Motivation

Wafer test is a crucial step at the end of semiconductor frontend production, where a sequence of electrical measurements is applied to each device on the wafer. The result is a spatial dataset, which can be visualized by plotting the measured parameters for each device on the wafer at their corresponding x-y position, these images are called wafermaps. While wafermaps are commonly used by experts to judge the stability of the production, our intention is to detect spatial patterns on the analog measurement data, as they might reveal deviations in the production process. We aim to quantify patterns with respect to their intensities, indicating the evolution level of a spatial process pattern. This will be achieved by calculating two statistical key figures, Spatial Entropy and Moran's I, which we apply to simulated data, as well as to a real-world dataset demonstrating the applicability of each method.

Description

We define the intensity of a pattern by two distinct aspects: the relative range of the measurement values compared to their specification limits (z-intensity), as well as the spatial distribution (x-y-intensity) of conspicuous values over the wafer.

Both, the Spatial Entropy and Moran's I are rotation invariant, whereas additionally, Moran's I is invariant w.r.t. spatial translation.

Spatial Entropy In statistics, entropy is a measure of uncertainty of a random variable X , see Cover [1]. The lower the entropy, the more information is available in advance. The entropy does not take spatial information into account and therefore assigns the same values for e.g. the two wafermaps in Figure 2, although a pattern is visible solely on the right wafermap.

To resolve this issue for spatial data, the Spatial Entropy was invented by Li [2] and Wang [3]. Here, a weighting factor (spatial diversity coefficient) is introduced:

$$Entropy_s(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{d_i^{int}}{d_i^{ext}} P_i \log_2 P_i .$$

To account for the spatial information, the devices are assigned to different equidistant bins by their measurement values, where n is the number of bins, d_i^{int} is the average intra distance of bin i and d_i^{ext} is the average extra distance of bin i (average distance between elements inside and outside bin i). P_i denotes the probability that a realization of X is assigned to bin i .

Moran's I This is a measure for spatial autocorrelation based on feature locations and values (see Goodchild [4]) The measure is bounded by $[-1, 1]$ and evaluates if a wafermap x shows a clustered (>0), dispersed (<0) or random (~ 0) pattern. The index is calculated via the formula

$$I = \frac{N}{\sum_i \sum_j w_{ij}} \frac{\sum_i \sum_j w_{ij} (x_i - \bar{x})(x_j - \bar{x})}{\sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2},$$

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where, N is the number of devices on the wafer, w_{ij} are scalar quantities, representing spatial weights with $w_{ii} = 0$, and \bar{x} is the mean of x .

Innovation

Up to now, state of the art methods regarding pattern recognition are available especially for binary data (pass/fail) but hardly cover to provide a rating for the intensities of patterns in analog data. Therefore, we are able to objectively detect process patterns before they provoke a yield loss and enable a faster reaction to process deviations. In summary, we propose a decision support system for experts to judge the intensity of a process pattern in an automated way.

Results

To evaluate Spatial Entropy and Moran's I on wafer test data, two simulated as well as one real dataset are used, each consisting of 12 wafermaps, see Figure 3. For verification, the Spearman's Rank-Order correlation coefficient is calculated based on the ground truth of the simulations. Both, Spatial Entropy, and Moran's I yield accurate results, see Table 1. The negative value of the Spatial Entropy in dataset "Simulation 1" is a consequence of negative correlation – the stronger the pattern is on the wafermap, the smaller is the Spatial Entropy, whereas in dataset "Simulation 2" we have a constant "z" intensity but vary the area of the pattern, which is positively correlated. Table 1 provides an overview on the characteristics of the investigated datasets. With a Spearman's correlation coefficient of -0.951 and a Moran's I of 0.776 compared to an optical ranking of the wafermaps (because the ground truth is not known), the "Real World Dataset" also yields an appropriate result. Furthermore, both methods are able to distinguish between real patterns and noise.

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References

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Figure 1: All three wafermaps show the same pattern (a “point” pattern) with different intensity levels w.r.t the “z” (wafermap 1 and 2) and the “x-y” spread (wafermap 1 and 3).

Figure 2: Two wafermaps with same entropy values.

	Pattern Characteristics			Spearman's correlation coefficient	
	Position	Size (x-y)	Size (z)	Spatial Entropy	Moran's I
Simulation 1	variable	fixed	variable	-0.885	0.972
Simulation 2	variable	variable	fixed	0.94	0.995
Real World Dataset				-0.951	0.776

Table 1 provides an overview on the characteristics of the simulated datasets. We take into account the position, the spatial spread (size x-y) and the measurement values (size z) of the process patterns on the wafermaps, denoted by “variable” or “fixed” for the simulation datasets. For the “Real World Dataset” no ground truth exists; the ranking for the Spearman's correlation coefficient is based on an optical ordering of the wafermaps.

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Figure 3: The wafermaps of the simulations and the real dataset are ordered by the values of Spatial Entropy (left) and Moran's I (right).